

Synthesis and Characterisation of some Transition Metal Complexes of *N,N'*-Bis(2-aminobenzoyl)ethylenediamine

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Manuscript received 12 August 1993

Novel complexes of *N,N'*-bis(2-aminobenzoyl)ethylenediamine with some bivalent and trivalent transition metal ions have been synthesised. All the compounds have been characterised using elemental analysis, magnetic, ir, electronic and epr spectral studies.

The coordination chemistry of amide group has received much attention due to its diverse coordinating behaviour and the role it plays in biological process¹. An amide group offers two potential binding sites, i.e. through oxygen and nitrogen for complexation with protons and metal ions. It is now generally accepted that for neutral amide groups, both protonation and metal ion binding will be at the amide oxygen^{2,3}. Upon deprotonation, the binding shifts to the amide nitrogen⁴. But for certain reasons, like bite size and steric hindrance, the coordination may also take place at amide nitrogen⁵.

Bis-amide tetradenate ligands with carboxyl anchors have interesting coordinating properties, i.e. they form monomeric complexes with most of the transition metal ions except Cu^{II} in which case dimers are formed with two metal ions exchange coupled⁶. In Cu^{II} case, they simply form carboxylate type dimers⁷ with subnormal magnetic moment values. In view of these differences, further investigations of the coordination behaviour of the amide group is worthwhile.

Fig. 1. Structure of Baben

In our continuing studies of metal-amide interactions³⁻⁶, we report here the synthesis and spectroscopic studies of the complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} ions with *N,N'*-bis(2-aminobenzoyl)ethylenediamine (Baben) (Fig. 1).

Results and Discussion

All the complexes formed were powders or microcrystalline, stable at atmospheric conditions and soluble in alcohol, DMF and DMSO. Analytical results were satisfactory and possible composition is presented in Table 1. Table 2 presents the magnetic, ir and electronic spectral data of the complexes.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE LIGAND AND COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p. °C	μ_{eff} B. M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	M
1.	Baben	242	—	64.40 (64.42)	5.98 6.04	18.62 18.80	—
2.	[Cr(Baben)Cl ₂]Cl	280	3.90	42.00 (42.06)	3.69 3.94	12.12 12.26	11.28 11.39
3.	[Mn(Baben)Cl ₂]Cl	270	2.80	41.60 (41.78)	3.83 3.91	12.09 12.18	11.90 11.97

Table-1. cont'd.

4	[Fe(Baben)Cl ₂]Cl	275	2.40	41.58 (41.70)	3.83 3.90	12.08 12.16	12.10 12.13
5	[Co(Baben)](OAc) ₂	310	2.32	50.41 (50.53)	5.00 5.05	11.63 11.79	12.28 12.42
6	[Ni(Baben)](OAc) ₂	320	Dia	50.44 (50.56)	5.00 5.06	11.76 11.81	12.23 12.36
7	[Cu(Baben)(H ₂ O) ₂] (OAc) ₂	300	1.90	46.43 (46.55)	5.40 5.53	10.77 10.86	12.26 12.33
8	[Zn(Baben)(H ₂ O) ₂] (OAc) ₂	305	Dia.	46.29 (46.42)	5.37 5.42	10.66 10.83	12.44 12.57
9	[Pd(Baben)]Cl ₂	295	Dia	40.24 (40.42)	3.63 3.79	11.70 11.78	22.28 22.38

^aRef 7 ^bRef 8TABLE 2-IR AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF COMPLEXES

Sl no	Compd	ν_{NH} amine	ν_{NH} amide	amide-I	amide-II	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ / $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$	λ_{max}	Assignment
1	Baben	3 450, 3 350	3 280	1 625	1 540	-	-		
2	[Cr(Baben)Cl ₂]Cl	3 360, 3 280	3 210	1 625	1 510	525	(327)	20 900 27 560	⁴ T _{2g} ← ⁴ T _{2g} ⁴ T _{1g} (F) ← ⁴ A _{2g}
3	[Mn(Baben)Cl ₂]Cl	3 360, 3 290	3 210	1 630	1 515	527	(330)	11 800 24 000	-
4	[Fe(Baben)Cl ₂]Cl	3 350, 3 280	3 210	1 625	1 520	528	(325)	21 050 36 230	⁴ T _{1g} ← ² T _{2g} ² E _g ← ² T _{2g}
5	[Co(Baben)](OAc) ₂	3 380, 3 290	3 220	1 630	1 520	510	-	8 600 22 700 26 700	-
6	[Ni(Baben)](OAc) ₂	3 380, 3 330	3 215	1 625	1 525	520		22 075	³ B _{2g} ← ¹ A _{1g}
7	[Cu(Baben)(H ₂ O) ₂] ²⁺	3 390, 3 310	3 220	1 625	1 520	510	420	15 600	² T _{2g} ← ² E _g
8	[Zn(Baben)(H ₂ O) ₂] ²⁺	3 390, 3 300	3 220	1 625	1 520	510	415	-	-
9	[Pd(Baben)]Cl ₂	3 390, 3 300	3 220	1 630	1 530	530		15 800	¹ A _{2g} ← ¹ A _{1g}

The ligand has a medium intensity band in the ~ 3 280 cm⁻¹ region and a doublet at 3 450 and 3 550 cm⁻¹ revealing the presence of NH of amide group and aromatic NH₂ groups. These bands show a negative shifts of 50- 100 cm⁻¹ upon complexation indicating coordination through nitrogen of the amide group⁸ and aromatic NH₂ groups⁹. In addition, the C-N band, i.e. amide-II band centered at 1 540 cm⁻¹ also shifts to lower frequency by 30 cm⁻¹ supporting the amide-nitrogen coordination

Further, amide-I band ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$) centered at 1 625 cm⁻¹ shows no shift upon complexation ruling out the coordination through amide oxygen. The spectra of the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes display a band at 3 400 cm⁻¹ which reveals the presence of coordinated water. Far-ir spectra show the bands corresponding to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ stretching frequencies¹⁰.

Visible spectra of these complexes were recorded in methanol. The spectra of all the

complexes show charge transfer bands at 23 250 and 30 300 cm^{-1} besides $d-d$ transitions.

The Cr^{III} complexes show the magnetic moment value of 3.90 B.M. at room temperature. The electronic spectral bands at 20 900 and 27 560 cm^{-1} were assigned for ${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g} (\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g} (\nu_3)$ suggesting octahedral environment¹¹. The Mn^{III} complex shows the magnetic moment value of 2.89 B.M. at room temperature suggesting a low-spin system. The electronic spectral bands at 11 800 and 24 000 cm^{-1} are attributed ${}^4A_g \leftarrow {}^5B_{1g}$ and ${}^5T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^5B_{1g}$ transitions with N_4Cl_2 chromophore¹². The subnormal magnetic moment value for the Fe^{III} complex at room temperature suggests a low-spin environment. The two $d-d$ bands observed for the complexes are assigned for ${}^4T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ and ${}^2E_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ suggesting a distorted octahedral structure¹³. The Co^{II} complex shows a magnetic moment value of 2.34 B.M. at room temperature. The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex possess bands around 8 600, 22 700 and 26 700 cm^{-1} suggesting a low-spin four-coordinate complex¹⁴. Square-planar Co^{II} chelates have magnetic moments in the region 2.2–2.7 B.M. at room temperature¹⁵ and exhibit absorption at three different energies¹⁴. The Ni^{II} complex is diamagnetic and has shown only one $d-d$ band observed around 22 100 cm^{-1} and is assigned to ${}^1B_{1g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$. This reveals that Ni^{II} is present in square-planar environment. The Pd^{II} complex is also found to be diamagnetic with a $d-d$ transition at 15 800 cm^{-1} which is assigned for ${}^1A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ suggesting a square-planar environment¹⁶. The Cu^{II} complex shows a magnetic moment value of 1.90 B.M. corresponding to the presence of one unpaired electron. The electronic spectra of the complex possess one broad band around 15 600 cm^{-1} suggesting distorted octahe-

dral environment and is assigned¹² for ${}^{12}T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2E_g$. The Zn^{II} complex is diamagnetic as expected and no $d-d$ bands consequent upon crystal field effects¹⁷.

Epr spectra : The epr spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes were studied at 298 and 165 K. The Cu^{II} complex shows two signals suggesting axial symmetry. The g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and $\langle g \rangle$ and A_{\parallel} , A_{\perp} and $\langle A \rangle$ and G values are given in Table 3.

The $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0023$ observed for the Cu^{II} complex indicates that the unpaired electron most likely resides in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital, thus implying a ${}^2B_{1g}$ ground state¹⁸. G , a measure of exchange interaction, being < 4 , indicates considerable exchange interaction in solid complex¹⁹. We have calculated α^2 by using simple relationship²⁰,

$$\langle g \rangle = 2.0023 - [8 \lambda \alpha^2 / \Delta ({}^2T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2E_g)]$$

The quantity α^2 is a function which depends on the nature of the copper ligand bond, decreasing with increasing covalency from 1.0 to a minimum theoretical value of 0.50. The present complexes seems to be fairly covalent, α^2 being 0.63–0.66.

In thermal studies of all the complexes, only the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complex shows weight-loss around 150° indicating the loss of coordinated water. Endothermic peaks in DTA supports the loss of water²¹. All the complexes are thermally stable upto 290° .

In the light of recorded experimental data and from converging arguments made above it is concluded that the ligand Baben acts as a neutral tetradentate ligand. Based on the analytic magnetic and spectral data it is proposed that Cr^{III} , Mn^{III} and Fe^{III} form a disturbed octahedral structure and Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} from square-planar and Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}

TABLE 3—EPR SPECTRAL PARAMETERS OF Cu^{II} COMPLEX

Compd.	Temp.	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	$\langle g \rangle$	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	$\langle a \rangle$	α^2	G
$\text{Cu}[\text{Baben}](\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$	298	2.49	2.16	2.27	223.00	45.00	105	0.63	3.06
$\text{Cu}[\text{Baben}](\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$	163	2.51	2.28	2.28	216.66	58.33	110	0.66	3.00

form octahedral complexes as shown in Fig. 2. In the absence of material suitable for single crystal studies the structures proposed are highly conjectural.

Fig. 2. Structures of the complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used were of A. R. grade. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 783 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Beckman DU-64 spectrophotometer and epr spectra on a JEOL-JES3X EPR spectrometer. Magnetic susceptibility at room temperature was measured with a Princeton 155 vibrating sample magnetometer.

Synthesis of ligand and complexes : The free ligand was synthesised by adding ethylene diamine to hot methanolic solution of isatoic anhydride in 1 : 2 molar proportions. The metal complexes were prepared by reacting the methanolic solutions of Baben with metal salts in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The coloured solid complexes formed were washed with acetone.

The metal salts used were chlorides of Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III} and Pd^{II} and acetates of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (M.J.R. and V.K.) are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Senior Research Fellowships.

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